

Factors Affecting Students' Interest in Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to describe the factors that influence students' entrepreneurial interest. The method in this research is a literature study with descriptive methods. The journals used in this research consisted of 9 journals with similar research themes, namely factors that influence students' interest in entrepreneurship. The results obtained in this research are that students' interest in entrepreneurship can develop due to two factors, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors include personal (internal), university, external and information, self-efficacy, freedom to work, visionary, expertise. Considering that universities have quite a large influence, entrepreneurship courses and programs in universities should be made as good as possible to foster entrepreneurial interest among students. Besides, the values and encouragement that individuals have regarding the social conditions around them will trigger them to think and do something. The implication of this research is to provide knowledge of factors that can support the formation of interest in entrepreneurship in students.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is one of the important things in developing a country's socioeconomic growth (Peterson & Lee, 2000). Entrepreneurship is considered to be able to help provide many job opportunities, increase prosperity and the level of competition in a country, various consumer needs, and services. Apart from that, entrepreneurship is also increasingly becoming an important concern in facing the challenges of globalization, namely global economic competition in terms of creativity and innovation (Peterson & Lee, 2000). This is because organizations that are skilled at innovation, successful in producing new ideas, will gain a competitive advantage and will not be left behind in the world market which continues to change rapidly (West, 1997). Thus, Suryana (2006) also states entrepreneurship as the ability to create added value in the market through the process of combining resources in new and different ways.

The entrepreneurial growth of a country is also the responsibility of the role of universities which educate and provide entrepreneurial skills to their graduates and provide motivation to dare to choose entrepreneurship for their students. Thus, a university of course needs to implement concrete entrepreneurial learning patterns to equip students with meaningful knowledge in order to encourage students' enthusiasm for entrepreneurship (Sudirman, et al, 2018). In this case, universities are expected to be able to change students' mindsets and instill entrepreneurial values that will shape the character and behavior for entrepreneurship or have the characteristics of being an entrepreneur, although this attitude is not fully applied as an entrepreneur (Misrah, 2019). However, in reality, there are still more college graduates who want to find work than can create their own jobs by becoming entrepreneurs. Based on a survey by the Central Executive Board of the Indonesian Young Entrepreneurs Association (BPP Hipmi), 83 percent of student respondents tend to want to become employees. Meanwhile, only 4 percent are interested in becoming entrepreneurs (Republika, 2016). One thing that influences this phenomenon is students' interest in entrepreneurship. Becoming an entrepreneur requires growing interest, and is followed by the availability of capital. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), interest is a response to an object that shows the customer's desire to do something, in this case entrepreneurship. To foster an interest in entrepreneurship in a student, it is necessary to provide motivation and knowledge about entrepreneurship, experience to become an entrepreneur directly, and also an environment that supports it, be it the school, family or community environment.

Santoso (2016) states that interest in entrepreneurship is an inner desire to fulfill life's needs, advance one's business or create a new business with one's own strengths. Furthermore, Santoso (2016) also states that interest in entrepreneurship is the tendency of the subject's heart to be interested in creating a business that then organizes, regulates, bears the risks and develops the business it creates. The phenomenon of low interest in entrepreneurship has become a serious consideration for various parties, including the government, education, industry and society. Various efforts have been made to foster interest in entrepreneurship, especially changing the mindset of students who

are only interested in being job seekers when they have completed their studies. Therefore, researchers are interested in conducting research to find out the factors that can influence the growth of interest in entrepreneurship among students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Fuadi (Rosmiati, Dony T & Munawar, 2015) interest in entrepreneurship is the desire, interest, and willingness to work hard or have a strong will to try optimally to fulfill one's life needs without feeling afraid of the risks that will occur, as well as the willingness to learn from failure. Interest in becoming an entrepreneur is defined as a person's desire to work independently or run their own business. Entrepreneurial Interest according to Slameto (Djaali, 2007), namely interest is a feeling of preference and interest in something without the involvement of parties who influence it. Another definition of interest is an agreement on a relationship between oneself and something outside oneself.

Entrepreneurial interest is the desire, interest, and willingness to work hard or be willing to try to fulfill one's life needs without feeling afraid of the risks one will face, learn from the failures one experiences, and develop the business one creates. Interest in entrepreneurship can be seen from the willingness to work hard and to achieve progress in one's business, the willingness to bear various risks related to the actions one takes. The definition of interest was also conveyed by Winkel & Srihastuti (2004), namely a tendency that is slightly stronger in a person to have a feeling of interest in something and a feeling of liking to socialize in various activities related to that field.

Interest in entrepreneurship is not inborn but grows and develops according to influencing factors. Factors that influence the growth of the decision to become an entrepreneur are the result of the interaction of several factors, namely a person's personality and their environment (Bygrave, 2003). Hisrich, et al. (2005) and Alma (2010) stated that the factors that influence entrepreneurial interest are the educational environment, a person's personality and the family environment. A person's interest in entrepreneurship can be seen from two main indicators, namely: 1. how strong a person's efforts are to dare to try to carry out entrepreneurial activities; 2. how much effort a person plans to put into entrepreneurial activities (such as activities in managing time and finances for entrepreneurial purposes).

METHODOLOGY

The method used is library research. This research is a type of library research, namely research whose object of study uses library data in the form of books as a data source (Hadi, 2022). This research was carried out by reading, reviewing and analyzing various existing literature, in the form of articles published in journals and books related to the theme of factors that influence students' interest in entrepreneurship. There are 9 journals which are international journals taken from several databases such as ScienceDirect, Taylor & Francis, Springer. The author searches directly from the website or

also uses the help of Google Scholar and Research Gate. The process itself goes through three processes, namely: editing, organizing, and discovery (Sarah Adilah Wandansari, Hernawati, 2021).

RESEARCH RESULT

Based on the results of a review of 9 journals related to work readiness and industrial practices, the following results were obtained:

Table 1. Results of a review of 9 journals related to work readiness and industrial practices

No	Name	Title Subject	Method	Results and Conclusions
1	Esti Dwi Rinawiyanti, Linda Herawati Gunawan	Identify factors that trigger entrepreneurial interest in students	This research was conducted to identify factors that can trigger entrepreneurial interest in students, especially at the University of Surabaya. Analysis was carried out on data obtained from distributing questionnaires to 405 students including descriptive analysis, importance level analysis and factor analysis.	From the analysis of the level of importance and factor analysis, several main factors were obtained that could arouse entrepreneurial interest in students which were grouped into four factors, namely personal (internal), university, external and information. Considering that universities have quite a large influence, entrepreneurship courses and programs in universities should be made as good as possible to foster entrepreneurial interest among students.
2	Jadmiko,Purb o.,Utami,Wiry.,Putri, Tyara Dwi.,Davizy, Ridhatulghina	Interest in social entrepreneurship : an empirical study Among students at various universities Public and private high	This study used 316 respondents spread from various public and private universities in Indonesia. Methods of data collection with survey techniques with the help of google form. Analysis of the data in this study using multiple regression	The results showed that prosocia motivation, intrinsic motivation, and moral obligation had a positive effect on students' interest in becoming social entrepreneurs . The implications of this research result can be used by universities to develop entrepreneurship education curriculum

			techniques.	in various social learning activities. Students' empathy and awareness can be developed through social entrepreneurship education programs
3	Sudirman L Damirah, I Nyoman Budiono	Developing entrepreneurial interest in students State Islamic Religious High School (Stain) Parepare	This research uses explanatory research. The results of research showed that 9% of STAIN parepare students have been doing entrepreneurial activities in addition to perform their main duties as students.	The results of the test together show that the variables of entrepreneurship subject consist of seminar/ training; religious approach; student Entrepreneurship Development Center; student cooperative; cooperation with financial institution, cooperation with business institution, capital aid, lecturer enhancement, and side job together affect student interest in entrepreneurship.
4	I Komang Sumerta, Ni Komang Redianingsih, I Made Baji Pranawa, Desak Nyoman Tri Indahyani	Influence of level of social media use and motivation Towards interest in entrepreneurship among program students Study of higher education management in the city of Denpasar	This research carried out at the Management Study Program College located in the Denpasar City area. The sample used is as many as 100 students WA is active in the management study program high school in the city of Denpasar. The data analysis techniques used are Multiple Linear	The results of analysis in this study indicate the level of use of Social Media has a positive and partially significant effect on Entrepreneurial Interest, it can be seen from the t-value of the variable Organizational Commitment is 8.417 is greater than the t-table value of 1.661. Motivation has a positive and partially significant effect on Entrepreneurial Interest,

			Regression Analysis, Coefficient of Determination, F Test and t Test.	it can be seen from the t-count value of Organizational Culture variables is 5.736 greater than the t-table value of 1.661
5	Yuhendri L.V.	Differences in Students' Entrepreneurial Interests Judging from Type Gender and Occupation of Parents	This study aims to look at the differences in entrepreneur interest of student of economic faculty of UNP based on sex and occupation of parents. The research is also useful for increasing the student's entrepreneur interest by taking into sex and occupation of parents. The kind of the research is comparative research	The research of the study showed that there are the differences in the entrepreneur interest between the male student and female student. Meanwhile there is no difference student's entrepreneur interest based on parent's occupation.
6	Retno Budi Lestari dan Trisnadi Wijaya.	The Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on Student Entrepreneurial Interests at STIE MDP, STMIK MDP, and STIE MUSI	This study aims to determine the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention. Data collection techniques use a questionnaire given to 205 students from three private universities namely STIE MDP, STMIK MDP, and STIE Musi	The results of hypothesis test shows that entrepreneurship education has a significant influence on entrepreneurial intention shown by the calculated F greater than F table, so the hypothesis of the study is accepted. Entrepreneurial intention is also reinforced by the demographic variables of gender, work experience, and parent's occupation. Entrepreneurial intention of men is higher than women. Students who have work experience also have a higher entrepreneurial intention. Students whose parents work as

				farmers have the most entrepreneurial intention.
7	Retno Kadarsih, - Susilaningsih, Sri Sumaryati_	Factors influencing interest in entrepreneurship in students of the fkip uns economic education study program	This research uses quantitative descriptive methods. The population of this study were students from the Economic Education Study Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Sebelas Maret University who had taken entrepreneurship courses. Sampling was taken using Proportional Random Sampling Technique. The sample in this research consisted of 100 students. The data collection techniques used were questionnaires, observation and documentation. The data analysis technique used to measure interest in entrepreneurship uses the Ajzen formula, while to look for factors that influence interest in entrepreneurship using factor analysis called Exploratory Factor Analysis.	Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, students' interest in entrepreneurship is classified as high, namely (1) 96%, the rest are classified as moderate interest in entrepreneurship. (2) Factors that influence students' interest in entrepreneurship include (a) self-efficacy, (b) freedom to work, (c) visionary, (d) expertise, (e) availability of capital and social environment, (f) contextual, and (g) perception of the entrepreneur figure.
8	Febrianto	Analysis Of Student Interest In Entrepreneurship Stie East Lampung	Data analysis techniques used in This research is by adding and find the average of the questionnaire answers	College as one of the means and facilitating role in shaping the young generation has an obligation to train and motivate the students to give to become savvy

		<p>has been given to the respondent. Questionnaire is used as a tool for measure someone's interest in entrepreneurship</p>	<p>generation, independent, creative, innovative and able to make a variety of business opportunities. Therefore, each college immediately balance the college policy direction between institutions of college research institutions forming businessman. Students after graduation claimed to be more innovative and creative in terms of their personal development through the creation of level playing field, so that future expected with extensive job creation, economic growth in the region will also increase and poverty will decrease.</p>	
9	Misrah	<p>Analysis of Entrepreneurial Interests of 2015-2018 Economic Education Students, Faculty of Economics, Makassar State University</p>	<p>This research was conducted with The aim is to find out how interested in entrepreneurship the 2015-2018 students are economic education, Faculty of Economics, Makassar State University. The research method used is descriptive qualitative research Data collection is through observation and questionnaires</p>	<p>The research results show that there is interest in entrepreneurship students from the 2015-2018 class can grow and increase their interest in entrepreneurship for students because of the internal and external factors of each student and proven by the majority of respondents having a high interest in entrepreneurship, namely external factors were 34 out of 54 respondents (63.1%). This shows that with there are external factors in the form of encouragement from parents and influence from the surrounding</p>

DISCUSSION

Based on the research results, it is known that research by Esti Dwi Rinawiyanti, Linda Herawati Gunawan (2017) shows that From the analysis of the level of importance and factor analysis, several main factors were obtained that could arouse entrepreneurial interest in students which were grouped into four factors, namely personal (internal), university, external and information. Considering that universities have quite a large influence, entrepreneurship courses and programs in universities should be made as good as possible to foster entrepreneurial interest among students. Similar research results were also obtained by Misrah (2019) which showed that there is interest in entrepreneurship students from the 2015-2018 class can grow and increase their interest in entrepreneurship for students because of the internal and external factors of each student and proven by the majority of respondents having a high interest in entrepreneurship, namely external factors were 34 out of 54 respondents (63.1%). This shows that with there are external factors in the form of encouragement from parents and influence from the surrounding environment.

Previous research by Sieger et al (2011) also shows that there are several factors that influence entrepreneurial interest in students, namely motivation, family background and constraints, where these three factors will shape behavior, attitudes and norms that influence interest. businessman. Internal factors originating from within the entrepreneur can be in the form of personal traits, attitudes, willingness and individual abilities which can give the individual strength to become an entrepreneur. Meanwhile, external factors come from outside the entrepreneur, which can be elements from the surrounding environment, such as the family environment, business environment, physical environment, socio-economic environment, etc.

Research by Yamini et al., (2020); Ayob et al., (2013); Jadmiko et al., (2022). Prosocial motivation perceived by students can increase interest in becoming a social entrepreneur. Prosocial motivation can be perceived as encouraging them to contribute to doing something about the conditions around them. The values and encouragement that individuals have regarding the social conditions around them will trigger them to think and do something. This finding is in accordance with the research results of Yamini et al., (2020) and Ayob et al., (2013) which show that intrinsic motivation has a positive effect on social entrepreneurial intention. In this way, universities are expected to be more active in creating an entrepreneurial environment on campus that can arouse the entrepreneurial spirit in students, including by providing adequate infrastructure and resources and creating a conducive environment that can shape students' entrepreneurial mindset.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this research is that students' interest in entrepreneurship can develop due to two factors, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors include personal (internal), university, external and information, self-efficacy, freedom to work, visionary, expertise. Considering that universities have quite a large influence, entrepreneurship courses and programs in universities should be made as good as possible to foster entrepreneurial interest among students. Besides, the values and encouragement that individuals have regarding the social conditions around them will trigger them to think and do something.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Based on the results of this research, ongoing research can be carried out using quantitative methods to determine the magnitude of the influence of internal and external factors on students' interest in entrepreneurship. Apart from that, this research can also be continued with experimental research by increasing internal factors such as self-efficacy, information, or providing skills to increase students' interest in entrepreneurship.

REFERENCES

- Alma, B.(2011) *Entrepreneurship For Students and General*. Bandung:Alphabet
- Ayob, N., Yap, C.S., Sapuan, D.A.,& Rashid, M.Z.A. (2013). Social Entrepreneurial Intention among business graduates an emerging economy perspective. *Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business*, 15(3), 249-267
- Bygrave, W. D. .(2003).*The Portable MBA Entrepreneurship*. Jakarta: Binarupa Literacy
- Djaali. (2007). *Educational Psychology*.Jakarta: Bumi Literacy
- Febrianto (2013). Analysis Of Student Interest In Entrepreneurship Stie East Lampung. *Journal of Management and Business* Vol. 3 No. 2 April 2013 : 150-159
- Hadi, Sutrisno. (2002). *Research Methodology*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset
- Hisrich, R. D., et al. (2008).*Entrepreneurship*.Edition 7. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Jadmiko, Purbo., Utami, Wiry., Putri, Tyara Dwi., Davizy, Ridhatulghina. (2022). Interest in social entrepreneurship: empirical study among students at various state and private universities *Scientific Journal of Economics and Business* Vol. 19 No.2
- Jadmiko, P., Azliyanti, E., & Yuliviona, R. (2022). Predictors of Social Entrepreneurial Intention in Undergraduate Students in Padang City. *KnE Social Sciences*, 2022, 83-91. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v7i6.10611>
- Kadarsih, Retno., Susilaningsih.,Sumaryati,Sri.(2013). Factors influencing interest in entrepreneurship in students of the fkip uns economic education study program.*Jupe UNS*, Vol 2 No 1 Year 2013 Pages 95 to 106
_Retno Kadarsih_Factors that Influence Entrepreneurial Interest in

- Students of the Economic Education Study Program, FKIP UNS, August 2013
- Kompas.com. (2016). Increasing the Ideal Number of Indonesian Entrepreneurs. Retrieved January 28, 2018, from <http://Ekonomi.kompas.com>
- Kotler, P. (2012). *Marketing management*. Pearson Education International.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *A Framework for Marketing Management*. Marketing Management.
- Lestari, Retno Budi., & Wijaya, Trisnadi. (2012). The Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on Student Entrepreneurial Interests at STIE MDP, STMIK MDP, and STIE MUSI. *Forum Bisnis Dan Kewirausahaan Jurnal Ilmiah STIE MDP Vol 1 no.2*
- Misrah. (2019). Analysis of Entrepreneurial Interests of 2015-2018 Economic Education Students, Faculty of Economics, Makassar State University. <http://eprints.unm.ac.id/14997/1/JURNAL%20%28ARTIKEL%29%20MISRAN.pdf>
- Rinawiyanti, Esti Dwi., & Gunawan, Linda Herawati. (2017). Identification of Factors Triggering Entrepreneurial Interest in Students. *Business and Entrepreneurship Forum STIE MDP Scientific Journal* <https://forbiswira.stie-mdp.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/4.-PDF-Esti.pdf>
- Rosmiati, Dony T & Munawar. (2015). Attitude, Motivation and Interest in Entrepreneurship Students. *Journal of Management and Finance*, Vol.17, No. 1
- Santoso, S. (2016). *Entrepreneurship*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Sieger, P., U. Fueglistaller & T. Zellweger. 2011, *International Report of The Global University Entrepreneurial Spirit Student's Survey Project (GUESS 2011)*, University of St. Gallen
- Sudirman., Damirah., Budiono, I Nyoman. (2018). Pengembangan minat berwirausaha pada mahasiswa Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam Negeri (STAIN) Pare Pare. *Jurnal Syari'ah dan Hukum Diktum*, Volume 16, Nomor 1 Juli 2018 : 16-31 <https://ejurnal.iainpare.ac.id/index.php/diktum/article/view/519/391>
- Sumerta, I Komang., Redianingsih, Ni Komang., Pranawa, I Made Baji., Indahyani, Desak Nyoman Tri. (2020). Influence of level of social media use and motivation Towards interest in entrepreneurship among program students Study of higher education management in the city of Denpasar. SSN : 2337-3067E-*Journal of Economics and Business*, Udayana University 9.7(2020):627-652
- Winkel, WS & Srihastuti, M.M. (2004). *Guidance and counseling in Institutions Education*. Yogyakarta: Media Aba
- Yamini, R., Soloveva, D., & Peng, X. (2020). What Inspires Social Entrepreneurship? The Role of Prosocial Motivation, Intrinsic Motivation, and Gender in Forming Social Entrepreneurial Intention. In *Entrepreneurship Research Journal* (July Issue). <https://doi.org/10.1515/erj-2019->

Yuhendri L.V.(2015). Differences in Students' Entrepreneurial Interests Judging from Type Gender and Occupation of Parents. Available Online at <http://fe.unp.ac.id/Book of Proceedings> published by (c)National seminar on management and economics Accounting (snema) faculty of economics Padang state university Snema-2015 Padang-Indonesia.ISBN: 978-602-17129-5-5